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ABSTRACT

A fully numerical homogenization technique for the retrieval of the effective surface susceptibilities of a periodic composite metasurface is developed in this work. We utilize the so-called dual field-flux finite element formulation scheme to accurately calculate the eigenmodes of a composite periodic metasurface, a scheme that possesses a crucial advantage: The capability of evaluating all field components and their derivatives accurately and with the same order of approximation is a requirement for our proposed technique. Next, we derive the generalized sheet transition condition equations for a general bianisotropic metasurface, which correlate the field components on either sides of the metasurface with its surface susceptibilities. At this point, we establish a new field averaging scheme for the acquisition of the average field components of the modes supported by the metasurface. Combining this computational information, we derive a set of linear algebraic equations based on the GSTCs and the average electromagnetic fields and numerically solve it, so as to obtain the effective surface susceptibilities of a bianisotropic metasurface. Comparison with the results of other techniques in the literature shows very good agreement, relatively to the resonance behavior of the returned values and their position at the frequency spectrum. The advantages that distinguish the proposed technique over other related methods are its foundation on the intrinsic modal information of the eigenmodes supported by the metasurface and its independence of any wave excitation schemes or involvement of analytical polarizability calculations.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial structures, such as metasurfaces, have emerged over the past two decades and are found to offer enhanced control of electromagnetic waves well-beyond the capabilities of naturally occurring materials. They are two-dimensional versions of the volumetric metamaterials, and they have been designed, optimized, and implemented in a range of applications across the frequency spectrum. These include, among others, perfect absorbers, reflectors, waveguiding structures, leaky-wave antennas, phase shifters, switches, modulators, polarizers, lenses, etc.^{1–4} Furthermore, except for artificial magnetism, bianisotropy—as a result of spatial dispersion or nonreciprocity—is another phenomenon which is closely related to the concept of metasurfaces. A wide variety of functionalities and applications are offered by this category of bianisotropic

metasurfaces, such as polarization transformers, rotators, reflectors, etc., whereas, depending on their inclusion or not of identical unit cells, the classes of uniform and gradient metasurfaces have emerged, respectively.⁵

As regards 3D-periodic metamaterials, these composite media are properly modeled by their effective constitutive parameters, i.e., permittivity, permeability, and magnetoelectric coupling tensors $\bar{\epsilon}_r$, $\bar{\mu}_r$, and $\bar{\kappa}$, respectively. During the last decades, many alternative numerical, analytical, or semi-analytical techniques were proposed for the parameter retrieval of these composites.^{6–11} On the other hand, metasurface characterization or modeling consists of the procedure of finding the effective, macroscopic surface parameters of an equivalent homogeneous thin film that may substitute a composite, non-homogeneous metasurface. In the case of 2D-periodic metasurfaces, it has been proved that a metasurface cannot be

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properly characterized by its bulk effective parameters, due to their strong dependence on the thickness of the metasurface.^{12,13} Indeed, successful techniques of parameter retrieval in metamaterials fail to return unique parameter values when applied to metasurface characterization. On the contrary, the most effective means to properly characterize a metasurface appears to be the tensors of its electric, magnetic, and magnetoelectric surface susceptibilities $\overline{\chi}_{ee}$, $\overline{\chi}_{mm}$, and $\overline{\chi}_{me}$, respectively. Additionally, a powerful approach toward metasurface characterization has been shown to come in the form of the so-called generalized sheet transition conditions (GSTCs). Derived in Ref. 14, they consist of a set of equations which connect the electromagnetic field quantities above and below an electromagnetically thin surface with its surface susceptibilities.

A number of characterization techniques have been proposed for the retrieval of the metasurface susceptibilities. Most of them are based on the inversion of scattering coefficients, inspired by the Nicolson–Ross–Weir (NRW) method,^{15–17} which enable the treatment of structures displaying anisotropy. Moreover, models based on the analytical determination of the polarizabilities and susceptibilities of a metasurface were also proposed, with the ability to handle bianisotropic metasurfaces, as well.^{18–29} However, all of the aforementioned approaches are highly dependent on specific excitations of the metasurface, notably limiting their applicability. The purpose of the present work is to present a technique for metasurface characterization which is based solely on the supported eigenmodes, making it general and independent of any wave excitation schemes or analytical determinations of polarizability tensors, providing thus the full metasurface response and allowing to reveal possibilities and effects beyond those connected to any particular excitation scheme.

Specifically, we introduce and demonstrate a novel, consistent characterization technique for the extraction of the effective surface susceptibilities of a bianisotropic metasurface. In particular, this technique is based on the computational information provided by the eigensolution of the unit cell of a metasurface in question, combined with a proposed averaging process of the returned field distributions of its supported modes and allows for the extraction of electric, magnetic, and magnetoelectric tensorial surface susceptibilities. Our proposed technique makes use of the intrinsic behavior of the composite metastructure, as it utilizes the computational information of its supported modes. In this way, the technique makes no reference to a particular type of excitation or to any analytical determinations of polarizability matrices. As far as the basic principles of homogenization are fulfilled, cf. Sec. II, no other constraints or conditions need to be imposed in our technique, rendering its generality and rigorousness. The robustness of our approach consists of the fact that eigenmode analysis is considered superior, since the dispersion graphs carries all the information on the propagating modes and provides a correct representation of the electromagnetic fields in the periodic structure, which is in sharp contrast to the techniques that assume incidence of a uniform plane wave on the metasurface and return only a rough approximation of the structure's response.¹¹

The present work is organized as follows: We utilize the dual field-flux FEM formulations proposed in Refs. 11 and 30 as a tool to accurately calculate the eigenmodes of a composite periodic metasurface inside the irreducible Brillouin zone, in Sec. II A. This

way, computational information from both propagating modes (passbands) and evanescent modes (bandgaps) is feasible at orthogonal in-plane directions, with the guaranteed return of non-spurious solutions. Furthermore, as rigorously proved in the same section, a great advantage of the utilization of this approach, as opposed to the single-field formulation, is its correct evaluation of the derivatives of the field components, especially with respect to the same directions (e.g. the partial derivative of the x -component of the electric field with respect to the x -coordinate); a crucial feature required by the proposed technique. The returned dispersion diagrams and the field distributions of a periodic metasurface consisting of edge-coupled split-ring resonators (EC-SRRs) are illustrated in Sec. II B.

In Sec. III, the technique of metasurface characterization is outlined. Specifically, in Sec. III A, we derive the GSTC equations for the general case of a bianisotropic metastructure. Additionally, in Sec. III B, we establish the field averaging process in the case of metasurfaces, based on our previous rigorous field averaging procedure for 3D-periodic composite media¹¹ and the constraints that the GSTCs impose. We then propose, the integration areas where the microscopic fields need to be integrated, in order to obtain the average fields above and below the metasurface. The technique, therefore, consists of the expression of the GSTCs in a form of an algebraic system of equations to be solved, with the average field components as the coefficients and the effective surface susceptibilities as the unknowns. The results of the proposed technique are finally illustrated in Sec. III C for the case of the bianisotropic EC-SRR metasurface. Very good agreement is observed, compared to other computational and analytical techniques in the literature, with respect to the resonance behavior and the frequency spectrum position of the returned effective surface susceptibilities. Finally, a conclusion is included in Sec. IV. Throughout the work, the time-factor $\exp(j\omega t)$, with ω being the angular frequency and t being the time, is assumed and suppressed.

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II. METASURFACE EIGENMODE ANALYSIS

In this section, we first outline the computational tool for the acquisition of the metasurface eigenmodes and subsequently illustrate the approach through representative numerical results (dispersion diagrams and field distributions) for a particular metasurface consisting of EC-SRRs.

A. Field-flux FEM formulation

The utilized computational tool is inspired by our previously proposed field-flux FEM formulation for 3D-periodic metamaterials: the **e-b** formulation along with its dual counterpart, the **h-d** formulation, see Refs. 31–33 for all details. Presently, we derive the final eigenvalue problem cast in a matrix form, whereas we particularly stress on the necessity on the dual-field, rather than a single-field formulation for the purpose of this work. For a periodic medium (see Fig. 1), the modified Maxwell's equations in terms of the envelopes of the electromagnetic fields are

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{e} - j\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{e} = -j\omega \mathbf{b}, \quad (1a)$$

FIG. 1. (Left) Unit cell of the EC-SRR composite metasurface. The resonators are arranged on a tetragonal lattice (with an edge of $d = d_x = d_y = 7.5$ mm). Periodicity is imposed on xz and yz boundaries, whereas an absorbing boundary condition of first order terminates the xy boundaries of the computational domain. In-plane Bloch-Floquet wave incidence is illustrated along with the up and down integration volumes for the field averaging (Sec. III B). (Right) Dimensions of the EC-SRR (in mm): The metallic rings are made of copper and have a thickness of $17 \mu\text{m}$.

$$\nabla \times \bar{\mu}_r^{-1} \mathbf{b} - jk \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \bar{\mu}_r^{-1} \mathbf{b} = j\omega \epsilon_0 \mu_0 \bar{\epsilon}_r \mathbf{e}, \quad (1b)$$

where electric field intensity \mathbf{E} and magnetic flux density \mathbf{B} are connected with their respective periodic envelopes \mathbf{e} and \mathbf{b} as

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{e} e^{-jk \cdot \mathbf{r}}, \quad (2a)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{b} e^{-jk \cdot \mathbf{r}}. \quad (2b)$$

Here, $\bar{\epsilon}_r$ and $\bar{\mu}_r$ are the 3×3 tensors of relative permittivity and relative permeability, respectively, $\mathbf{k} = k \hat{\mathbf{k}}$ is the Bloch-Floquet wavevector of prescribed propagation direction $\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ (e.g., $\hat{\mathbf{k}} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}$), \mathbf{r} is the position vector, and $k = \beta - j\alpha$ is the unknown complex propagation constant. Assuming a computational domain of volume V , enclosed by a surface S , the final variational formulation (Galerkin style) is given as follows:

$$\iiint_V \mathbf{b}' \cdot \nabla \times \mathbf{e} \, dV - jk \iiint_V \mathbf{b}' \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{e} \, dV = -j\omega \iiint_V \mathbf{b}' \cdot \mathbf{b} \, dV, \quad (3a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \iiint_V \bar{\mu}_r^{-1} \mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla \times \mathbf{e}' \, dV - jk \iiint_V \mathbf{e}' \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \bar{\mu}_r^{-1} \mathbf{b} \, dV \\ & = j\omega \epsilon_0 \mu_0 \iiint_V \mathbf{e}' \cdot \bar{\epsilon}_r \mathbf{e} \, dV + \iint_S (\mathbf{e}' \times \bar{\mu}_r^{-1} \mathbf{b}) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} \, dS, \end{aligned} \quad (3b)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ denotes the unitary vector normal to the boundary, pointing outward from the boundary surfaces, ϵ_0 and μ_0 are the vacuum permittivity and permeability, respectively, and the primed fields \mathbf{e}' and \mathbf{b}' are the vectorial test functions for the electric field and the magnetic induction, respectively. It is noted that the calculation of the surface integral in Eq. (3b) depends on the type of boundary conditions that terminate the computational domain, which will be determined in Sec. II B.

We approximate this weak formulation with a finite dimensional problem, by discretizing the periodic envelopes of the electric

field and the magnetic flux density. \mathbf{e} is expanded in the finite dimensional subset of $H(\text{Curl}, \Omega)$, consisting of tangentially continuous edge-type basis functions of first order as $\mathbf{e} = \sum_{j=1}^6 e_j \mathbf{w}_j$, where \mathbf{w}_j are the basis functions corresponding to each one of the six tetrahedral edges (the first order basis function for edge $[ij]$ is $\mathbf{w}_{ij} = \zeta_i \nabla \zeta_j - \zeta_j \nabla \zeta_i$, with ζ_i being the simplex coordinate of the i^{th} node^{34–36}) and e_j are the degrees of freedom corresponding to each edge. \mathbf{b} is expanded in the finite dimensional subset of $H(\text{Div}, \Omega)$, consisting of normally continuous facet-type basis functions of first order as $\mathbf{b} = \sum_{l=1}^4 b_l \mathbf{v}_l$, where \mathbf{v}_l are the basis functions corresponding to each one of the four tetrahedral facets (the first order basis function for facet $[ijk]$ is $\mathbf{v}_{ijk} = \zeta_k \nabla \times \mathbf{w}_{ij} + \zeta_i \nabla \times \mathbf{w}_{jk} + \zeta_j \nabla \times \mathbf{w}_{ki}$, with ζ_i being the simplex coordinate of the i^{th} node^{34–36}) and b_l are the degrees of freedom corresponding to each facet. Using the same basis functions for the test fields $\mathbf{e}' = \sum_{i=1}^6 e'_i \mathbf{w}_i$ and $\mathbf{b}' = \sum_{k=1}^4 b'_k \mathbf{v}_k$, we derive the matrix form of the eigenvalue problem,

$$\begin{bmatrix} -j\omega \epsilon_0 \mu_0 \mathbf{T}^{EE} + \mathbf{T}_s^{EE} & \mathbf{Q}^{EB} - \mathbf{T}_s^{EB} \\ \mathbf{Q}^{BE} & j\omega \mathbf{T}^{BB} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E} \\ \mathbf{B} \end{bmatrix} = k \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -j\mathbf{P}^{EB} \\ -j\mathbf{P}^{BE} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E} \\ \mathbf{B} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

The corresponding submatrices are calculated as follows:³³

$$[\mathbf{Q}^{BE}] = \iiint_V \mathbf{v}'_k \cdot \nabla \times \mathbf{w}_j \, dV, \quad (5a)$$

$$[\mathbf{P}^{BE}] = \iiint_V \mathbf{v}'_k \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{w}_j \, dV, \quad (5b)$$

$$[\mathbf{T}^{BB}] = \iiint_V \mathbf{v}'_k \cdot \mathbf{v}_l \, dV, \quad (5c)$$

$$[\mathbf{Q}^{EB}] = \iiint_V \bar{\mu}_r^{-1} \mathbf{v}_l \cdot \nabla \times \mathbf{w}'_j \, dV, \quad (5d)$$

$$[\mathbf{P}^{EB}] = \iiint_V \mathbf{w}'_i \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \bar{\mu}_r^{-1} \mathbf{v}_l \, dV, \quad (5e)$$

$$[\mathbf{T}^{EE}] = \iiint_V \mathbf{w}'_i \cdot \bar{\epsilon}_r \mathbf{w}_j \, dV, \quad (5f)$$

$$[\mathbf{T}_s^{EB}] = \iint_S (\mathbf{w}'_i \times \bar{\mu}_r^{-1} \mathbf{v}_l) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} \, dS. \quad (5g)$$

The corresponding modified Maxwell's equations for the dual field-flux $\mathbf{h} - \mathbf{d}$ formulation, which utilizes the Bloch-Floquet envelopes of the magnetic field \mathbf{h} and the dielectric displacement \mathbf{d} as independent field variables are given as

$$\nabla \times \bar{\epsilon}_r^{-1} \mathbf{d} - jk \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \bar{\epsilon}_r^{-1} \mathbf{d} = -j\omega \epsilon_0 \mu_0 \bar{\mu}_r \mathbf{h}, \quad (6a)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{h} - jk\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{h} = j\omega\mathbf{d}, \quad (6b)$$

whereas the variational formulation for an identical computational domain is

$$\begin{aligned} & \iiint_V \nabla \times \mathbf{h}' \cdot \bar{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_r^{-1} \mathbf{d} \, dV - jk \iiint_V \mathbf{h}' \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \bar{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_r^{-1} \mathbf{d} \, dV \\ & = -j\omega\epsilon_0\mu_0 \iiint_V \mathbf{h}' \cdot \bar{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_t \mathbf{h} \, dV + \oint_S (\mathbf{h}' \times \bar{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_r^{-1} \mathbf{d}) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\text{ext}} \, dS, \end{aligned} \quad (7a)$$

$$\iiint_V \mathbf{d}' \cdot \nabla \times \mathbf{h} \, dV - jk \iiint_V \mathbf{d}' \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{h} \, dV = j\omega \iiint_V \mathbf{d}' \cdot \mathbf{d} \, dV. \quad (7b)$$

Again, calculation of the surface integral depends on the termination of the computational domain.

We now approximate this weak formulation with a finite dimensional problem, by discretizing the periodic envelopes of the magnetic field and the dielectric displacement. Expanding \mathbf{h} in the finite dimensional subset of $H(\text{Curl}, \Omega)$, consisting of tangentially continuous edge-type basis functions of first order as $\mathbf{h} = \sum_{j=1}^6 h_j \mathbf{w}_j$, where h_j are the degrees of freedom corresponding to each edge, and expand \mathbf{d} in the finite dimensional subset of $H(\text{Div}, \Omega)$, consisting of normally continuous facet-type basis functions of first order as $\mathbf{d} = \sum_{l=1}^4 d_l \mathbf{v}_l$, where d_l are the degrees of freedom corresponding to each facet, and using the same basis functions for the test fields $\mathbf{h}' = \sum_{i=1}^6 h'_i \mathbf{w}_i$ and $\mathbf{d}' = \sum_{k=1}^4 d'_k \mathbf{v}_k$, we derive the matrix form of the eigenvalue problem,

$$\begin{bmatrix} -j\omega \mathbf{T}^{D'D} & \mathbf{Q}^{D'H} \\ \mathbf{Q}^{H'D} - \mathbf{T}^S & j\omega \mathbf{T}^{H'H} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{D} \\ \mathbf{H} \end{bmatrix} = k \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{P}^{D'H} \\ \mathbf{P}^{H'D} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{D} \\ \mathbf{H} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

The corresponding submatrices may be calculated as follows:

$$[\mathbf{Q}^{D'H}] = \iiint_V \mathbf{v}'_k \cdot \nabla \times \mathbf{w}_j \, dV, \quad (9a)$$

$$[\mathbf{P}^{D'H}] = \iiint_V \mathbf{v}'_k \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{w}_j \, dV, \quad (9b)$$

$$[\mathbf{T}^{D'D}] = \iiint_V \mathbf{v}'_k \cdot \mathbf{v}_l \, dV, \quad (9c)$$

$$[\mathbf{Q}^{H'D}] = \iiint_V \bar{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_t^{-1} \mathbf{v}_l \cdot \nabla \times \mathbf{w}'_j \, dV, \quad (9d)$$

$$[\mathbf{P}^{H'D}] = \iiint_V \mathbf{w}'_i \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \bar{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_t^{-1} \mathbf{v}_l \, dV, \quad (9e)$$

$$[\mathbf{T}^{H'H}] = \iiint_V \mathbf{w}'_i \cdot \bar{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_t \mathbf{w}_j \, dV, \quad (9f)$$

$$[\mathbf{T}_S^{H'D}] = \oint_S (\mathbf{w}'_i \times \bar{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_t^{-1} \mathbf{v}_l) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} \, dS. \quad (9g)$$

Solutions of eigenvalue problems (4) and (8) provide us with the eigenpairs of complex propagation constants k and the corresponding field distributions all over the unit cell for every supported mode of the structure. We note that all FEM formulations were implemented in Comsol Multiphysics™ Weak Form.

According to Refs. 11, 30, and 32, utilization of both dual field-flux formulations is mandatory if the same order of accuracy is required for all four field quantities (\mathbf{e} , \mathbf{h} , \mathbf{d} , and \mathbf{b}): To maintain its order of approximation, without the requirement of any differentiation operation, a field quantity must be explicitly solved for in a FEM formulation, avoiding the utilization of Faraday–Maxwell’s or Ampère–Maxwell’s law. Furthermore, evaluation of any field quantity on the periodic boundaries of the computational domain should be carried out with respect to their own continuity type: Evaluating a normally continuous field component from a tangentially continuous one (e.g., \mathbf{D} from \mathbf{E}) leads to serious computational errors and should definitely be avoided. Here, a more significant reason is presented for the mandatory simultaneous numerical solution with the dual field-flux formulations. As it will become more clear in Sec. III, utilization of the GSTCs involves the evaluation of the partial derivatives of the field components, potentially with respect to the same direction (e.g., $\partial E_x / \partial x$). From the finite element theory,^{34–36} it is well known that only utilization of the divergence-conforming (H -div) basis functions guarantees the correct evaluation of this kind of derivatives, whereas the curl-conforming basis functions are not capable of their correct approximation (for the first order elements these derivatives are equal to zero). Indeed, the divergence-conforming elements are designed so as to properly model the divergence operator $\nabla \cdot = (\partial/\partial x)\hat{\mathbf{x}} + (\partial/\partial y)\hat{\mathbf{y}} + (\partial/\partial z)\hat{\mathbf{z}}$. This means that if, for example, we try to evaluate $\partial E_x / \partial x$ by expanding it with the typical curl-conforming (H -curl) functions, it will be forced to zero by default, which is, of course, a false result. The proposed way of evaluating this quantity as $(\partial D_x / \partial x) / \epsilon$ through the dielectric displacement field \mathbf{d} (for which we also solve for, as an independent field variable) avoids this severe numerical error.

B. Dispersion diagrams and field distributions for EC-SRR metasurface

To illustrate our technique, we consider a metasurface composed of EC-SRR unit cells, see Fig. 1. For this structure, its primitive Bravais lattice is a tetragonal lattice of edge $d = d_x = d_y$, whereas its corresponding reciprocal lattice is also a tetragonal lattice. The corresponding Brillouin zone is a square of edge $2\pi/d$ and its respective irreducible Brillouin zone forms an orthogonal triangle with nodes $(\Gamma - X - M - \Gamma)$.¹¹ The resonators are assumed to be $17\mu\text{m}$ thick, made of copper (conductivity $\sigma = 5.8 \times 10^7 \text{ S/m}$), embedded in free space and located in the xy plane. Periodic boundary conditions are imposed on xz and yz boundaries, whereas, the computational domain at xy boundaries is terminated by absorbing boundary conditions (ABCs) of first order, at a sufficient distance from the scatterers.³⁷ The computational domain is discretized by 23 232 tetrahedral elements,

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FIG. 2. Dispersion diagrams of the simulated EC-SRR metasurface for in-plane incidence k_x and k_y . Real (left) and imaginary (right) of the complex propagation constant $\gamma = \beta - j\alpha$. Both incidences' dispersion curves asymptotically tend to the lightline for the upper branch, as it is analytically predicted³⁸ (utilization of a denser FEM mesh is expected to provide a better numerical approximation of the returned eigenpairs at higher simulated frequencies.).

producing 374952 total degrees of freedom (edge and facet unknowns). Here, we stress that both FEM formulations [Eqs. (4) and (8)] return exactly identical solutions, when solved for identically discretized computational domains (identical FEM meshes, equal degrees of freedom, and eigensolver accuracies).

In Fig. 2, the dispersion diagrams of an EC-SRR metasurface are shown for the case of in-plane incidence (k_x and k_y wave vectors). These diagrams correspond to ΓX and XM paths of the irreducible Brillouin zone. Similar results are obtained for both incidence cases, confirming the results from the literature.³⁰ In particular, a bandgap is present between 8.1 and 8.5 GHz, exhibiting extremely evanescent modes (attenuation constant is larger than 50 Np/m), whereas the returned surface modes form the illustrated dispersion curve. In Fig. 3, the real part of the normal component of the electric field is depicted for the case of k_x incidence at 5 GHz, at xy planes precisely above and below the resonator. It is found that there is a sign change in the respective field distributions, in agreement with the mode distributions for the 3D-periodic case

FIG. 3. Real part of the E_z component above (left) and below (right) the EC-SRR unit cell at 5 GHz for the case of the k_x incidence. The sign change on the surfaces reveals the existence of a surface charge density.

reported in Ref. 30 and 39. Therefore, the existence of a surface charge distribution ρ_s is implied in the 2D-periodic case, as well, as exhibited by the non-zero result of the difference between the normal dielectric displacement vectors above and below the metasurface ($D_{z,1} - D_{z,2} = \rho_s$). It may be concluded that both orthogonal wave incidence dispersion diagrams and the associated mode distributions resemble the behavior of a 3D-periodic EC-SRR medium, confirming the findings of the existing literature.

III. METASURFACE CHARACTERIZATION TECHNIQUE

Here, we initially derive the GSTCs for an arbitrarily bianisotropic metasurface. Subsequently, a metasurface field averaging process is proposed and finally, the retrieval of the unknown surface susceptibilities is done by solving a system of linear equations.

A. GSTCs for a bianisotropic metasurface

As stated in Sec. I, scattering by a metasurface is appropriately characterized by the GSTCs. These conditions, introduced by Kuester *et al.*,¹⁴ connect the electromagnetic field components above and below a metasurface with its electric, magnetic, and magnetoelectric surface susceptibility tensors $\bar{\chi}_{ee}$, $\bar{\chi}_{mm}$, $\bar{\chi}_{em}$, and $\bar{\chi}_{me}$, respectively. Here, we derive these equations for the case of a general bianisotropic metasurface and utilize them, in conjunction with the dual-field FEM formulations of Sec. II, to retrieve the surface susceptibility tensors of an EC-SRR metasurface. Denoting the surface electric polarization density with \mathbf{P}_s , the surface magnetic polarization density with \mathbf{M}_s , the electric field above and below the metasurface with \mathbf{E}_+ , \mathbf{E}_- , respectively, and the corresponding magnetic fields with \mathbf{H}_+ , \mathbf{H}_- , respectively, the GSTCs may be written as follows:¹⁸

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \times (\mathbf{H}_+ - \mathbf{H}_-) = j\omega \mathbf{P}_{s,t} - \hat{\mathbf{n}} \times \nabla_t \mathbf{M}_{s,n}, \quad (10a)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \times (\mathbf{E}_+ - \mathbf{E}_-) = -j\omega \mu \mathbf{M}_{s,t} - \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \right) \hat{\mathbf{n}} \times \nabla_t \mathbf{P}_{s,n}, \quad (10b)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{D}_+ - \mathbf{D}_-) = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{P}_{s,t}, \quad (10c)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{B}_+ - \mathbf{B}_-) = \mu \nabla \cdot \mathbf{M}_{s,t}, \quad (10d)$$

where the subscripts t and n denote the tangential and normal parts of the vectors, respectively, and $\mu = \mu_0 \mu_r$. For the case of general bianisotropic scatterers, electric, and magnetic surface polarization densities are connected through the surface susceptibility tensors

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P}_s \\ \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \mathbf{M}_s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\chi}_{ee} & \bar{\chi}_{em} \\ \bar{\chi}_{me} & \bar{\chi}_{mm} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_0 \bar{\mathbf{E}} \\ \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \bar{\mathbf{H}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{E}} = (\mathbf{E}_+ + \mathbf{E}_-)/2$ and $\bar{\mathbf{H}} = (\mathbf{H}_+ + \mathbf{H}_-)/2$ are the mean electric and magnetic fields at the two sides of the metasurface,

respectively. Combining Eqs. (10) and (11), the GSTCs for the general case of a bianisotropic metasurface may be written as

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \times (\mathbf{H}_+ - \mathbf{H}_-) = j\omega \left[\epsilon_0 \langle \bar{\chi}_{ee} \bar{\mathbf{E}} \rangle_t + \frac{1}{c_0} \langle \bar{\chi}_{em} \bar{\mathbf{H}} \rangle_t \right] - \hat{\mathbf{n}} \times \nabla_t \left[\langle \bar{\chi}_{mm} \bar{\mathbf{H}} \rangle_n + c_0 \epsilon_0 \langle \bar{\chi}_{me} \bar{\mathbf{E}} \rangle_n \right], \quad (12a)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \times (\mathbf{E}_+ - \mathbf{E}_-) = -j\omega\mu \left[\langle \bar{\chi}_{mm} \bar{\mathbf{H}} \rangle_t + c_0 \epsilon_0 \langle \bar{\chi}_{me} \bar{\mathbf{E}} \rangle_t \right] - \hat{\mathbf{n}} \times \nabla_t \left[\epsilon_0 \langle \bar{\chi}_{ee} \bar{\mathbf{E}} \rangle_n + \frac{1}{c_0} \langle \bar{\chi}_{em} \bar{\mathbf{H}} \rangle_n \right], \quad (12b)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{D}_+ - \mathbf{D}_-) = -\nabla \cdot \left[\epsilon_0 \langle \bar{\chi}_{ee} \bar{\mathbf{E}} \rangle_t + \frac{1}{c_0} \langle \bar{\chi}_{em} \bar{\mathbf{H}} \rangle_t \right], \quad (12c)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{B}_+ - \mathbf{B}_-) = \mu \nabla \cdot \left[\langle \bar{\chi}_{mm} \bar{\mathbf{H}} \rangle_t + c_0 \epsilon_0 \langle \bar{\chi}_{me} \bar{\mathbf{E}} \rangle_t \right]. \quad (12d)$$

Equations (12) connect the field distributions on either sides of a bianisotropic surface. Acquisition of the values of the electromagnetic fields is carried out through the field averaging process proposed in the next section.

B. Field averaging

In Ref. 11, a field averaging technique was proposed for the case of 3D-periodic metamaterials. Under the homogenization conditions, i.e., the guided wavelength being much larger than the maximum edge of the unit cell ($\lambda_g \gg d$) and in the absence of higher order Bloch–Floquet modes, the fast-varying microscopic field quantities in a unit cell were successfully replaced by average and unique values, accounting for the wave–matter interaction. The paths of integration for the average quantities were selected to be the edges and the facets of the unit cell for the tangentially continuous and the normally continuous fields, respectively, inspired by the corresponding types of field continuity, under the prescription that the Maxwell’s equations in an integral form imply.

In the case of metasurface characterization, we are interested in its effective surface susceptibilities rather than its effective bulk parameters, so as a composite metastructure may be substituted by an effectively homogeneous thin film of infinitesimal thickness. To this end, we propose a means for proper averaging of the electromagnetic field quantities in the case of a metasurface. Here, we draw our inspiration from Eqs. (12): The required information in the case of a metasurface is the one that involves the electromagnetic fields’ distributions above and below the metastructure. Additionally, it is obvious that apart from the field distributions themselves, their spatial derivatives are also required. This numerical information exists inside the solutions returned by the dual FEM formulations outlined in Sec. II: When we solve for the unit cell of a composite periodic structure, evaluation of the (microscopic) field quantities is feasible at the mesh medians and, through interpolation, at every point of the computational domain. A closer look at Eqs. (12) reveals that field components and field derivatives are required above and below the metasurface at directions tangential and normal to the metasurface. Therefore, the selection of any possible integration regions should possess the ability to enclose all the required computational information on

either side of the structure, including potential differentiation with respect to arbitrary directions. For these reasons, we average the required field distributions over the volumes of the unit cell above and below the metasurface. For example (see Fig. 1), the average x component of the electric field E_x^+ above the metasurface is calculated by integrating the (microscopic, returned by the numerical solution) field distribution E_x inside the volume V_{up} above the metasurface as

$$E_x^+ = \frac{1}{V_{up}} \iiint_{V_{up}} E_x \, dV_{up}, \quad (13)$$

whereas the corresponding average component E_x^- is integrated inside the volume V_{down} below the metasurface and, respectively, calculated through

$$E_x^- = \frac{1}{V_{down}} \iiint_{V_{down}} E_x \, dV_{down}. \quad (14)$$

In Fig. 4, the dominant, average electric and magnetic field components of the examined EC-SRR metasurface are shown for both in-plane incidence cases (k_x and k_y). It is easily observed that there is a similar behavior of these components for both incidences (average E_y, H_z for k_x and average E_x, H_z for k_y incidence, respectively). Comparison with the corresponding dominant field components for the 3D-periodic metamaterial in Ref. 11 leads to a conclusion that all the dominant field components coincide for both incidence cases and have a very similar behavior of their magnitudes around the resonant frequencies. Therefore, along with the findings in Sec. II for the dispersion diagrams and the type of field distributions, we conclude that the operation of the investigated EC-SRR metasurface is based on the same surface mode which appears in the corresponding 3D-periodic metamaterial.

C. Retrieved surface susceptibilities for EC-SRR metasurface

To illustrate the proposed method, we now investigate a metasurface which meets the necessary homogenization requirements, cf. Sec. III B. A representative example of such a metasurface is the

FIG. 4. Absolute values of average electric field (left) and average magnetic field (right), above and below the metasurface for both in-plane incidences.

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EC-SRR metasurface analyzed in Sec. II. The eigenpairs (complex propagation constant and field distribution) of each of the modes supported by this metasurface are obtained through the solution of the associated eigenproblem by means of the dual field-flux FEM formulations. By utilizing the proposed field averaging process, acquisition of the average field components is feasible. Using the conclusions in Refs. 20 and 21 and taking into account that no nonreciprocal materials are included in the structure under consideration, the possible nonzero elements of the electric, magnetic, and magnetoelectric surface susceptibility tensors are

$$\bar{\chi}_{ee} = \begin{bmatrix} \chi_{ee}^{xx} & \chi_{ee}^{xy} & 0 \\ \chi_{ee}^{xy} & \chi_{ee}^{yy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \chi_{ee}^{zz} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (15a)$$

$$\bar{\chi}_{mm} = \begin{bmatrix} \chi_{mm}^{xx} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \chi_{mm}^{yy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \chi_{mm}^{zz} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (15b)$$

$$\bar{\chi}_{em} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \chi_{em}^{xz} \\ 0 & 0 & \chi_{em}^{yz} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (15c)$$

$$\bar{\chi}_{me} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\chi_{em}^{xz} & -\chi_{em}^{yz} & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (15d)$$

If we now focus on the dispersion diagrams of the EC-SRR metasurface, we find that for both k_x and k_y incidences, the metasurface supports a corresponding surface mode. For each one of these modes, we can therefore write Eqs. (12) and form the following system of algebraic equations:

$$j\omega\epsilon_0\bar{E}_x\chi_{ee}^{xx} + j\omega\epsilon_0\bar{E}_y\chi_{ee}^{xy} + j\frac{\omega}{c_0}\bar{H}_z\chi_{em}^{xz} + \frac{\partial\bar{H}_z}{\partial y}\chi_{mm}^{zz} - c_0\epsilon_0\frac{\partial\bar{E}_y}{\partial y}\chi_{em}^{yz} - c_0\epsilon_0\frac{\partial\bar{E}_x}{\partial y}\chi_{em}^{xz} = -H_y^+ + H_y^-, \quad (16a)$$

$$j\omega\epsilon_0\bar{E}_y\chi_{ee}^{yy} + j\omega\epsilon_0\bar{E}_x\chi_{ee}^{xy} + j\frac{\omega}{c_0}\bar{H}_z\chi_{em}^{yz} + \frac{\partial\bar{H}_z}{\partial x}\chi_{mm}^{zz} + c_0\epsilon_0\frac{\partial\bar{E}_y}{\partial x}\chi_{em}^{yz} + c_0\epsilon_0\frac{\partial\bar{E}_x}{\partial x}\chi_{em}^{xz} = H_x^+ - H_x^-, \quad (16b)$$

$$-j\omega\mu_0\bar{H}_x\chi_{mm}^{xx} + \frac{\partial\bar{E}_z}{\partial y}\chi_{ee}^{zz} = -E_y^+ + E_y^-, \quad (16c)$$

$$-j\omega\mu_0\bar{H}_y\chi_{mm}^{yy} - \frac{\partial\bar{E}_z}{\partial x}\chi_{ee}^{zz} = E_x^+ - E_x^-, \quad (16d)$$

FIG. 5. Retrieved non-zero surface susceptibilities for the EC-SRR metasurface. χ_{mm}^{zz} (left) is the dominant component, with a resonance frequency zone around 8 – 8.5 GHz (bandgap region). χ_{ee}^{yy} (middle) also exhibits resonant behavior for its real and imaginary parts, whereas χ_{em}^{yz} (right) has an antiresonant real part at the same frequency zone.

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$$-\varepsilon_0 \frac{\partial \overline{E}_x}{\partial x} \chi_{ee}^{xx} - \varepsilon_0 \frac{\partial \overline{E}_y}{\partial x} \chi_{ee}^{xy} - \frac{1}{c_0} \frac{\partial \overline{H}_z}{\partial x} \chi_{em}^{xz} - \varepsilon_0 \frac{\partial \overline{E}_y}{\partial y} \chi_{ee}^{yy} - \frac{1}{c_0} \frac{\partial \overline{H}_z}{\partial y} \chi_{em}^{yz} - \varepsilon_0 \frac{\partial \overline{E}_x}{\partial y} \chi_{ee}^{xy} = D_z^+ - D_z^-, \quad (16e)$$

$$\mu_0 \frac{\partial \overline{H}_x}{\partial x} \chi_{mm}^{xx} + \mu_0 \frac{\partial \overline{H}_y}{\partial y} \chi_{mm}^{yy} = B_z^+ - B_z^-. \quad (16f)$$

By writing (16) for both k_x and k_y incidence, the resulting equations can be cast into a linear system of the form $\mathbf{Ax} = \mathbf{B}$ involving 12 equations with 9 unknowns. The coefficients of matrix \mathbf{A} are the volume-averaged mean field quantities (overlined fields) and the column-matrix \mathbf{B} contains the volume-averaged field quantities above and below the metasurface (E_x^+ , E_y^- , etc.). To avoid possible confusion, it is noted that the known quantities (\mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} matrix elements) of the first six equations of the algebraic system (that refer to k_x incidence) are in general different from its last six equations (which correspond to k_y incidence). This means that they contain independent computational information. Obviously, this linear system of equations is overdetermined; therefore it has a unique solution if and only if $\text{rank}(\mathbf{A}) = \text{rank}([\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B}])$. In our case, an approximate solution is sought for, with, e.g., the least square method, which introduces an error of $|\mathbf{B} - \mathbf{Ax}|^2$.

We solve the linear system (16) to retrieve the effective surface susceptibilities of the EC-SRR metasurface. The returned non-zero parameters are shown in Fig. 5. The dominant surface susceptibility term is χ_{mm}^{zz} , with its real and imaginary parts following an expected resonant behavior around the bandgap frequency zone (8 – 8.5 GHz approximately). Additionally, χ_{ee}^{yy} follows a resonant behavior, as well, around the same frequencies, whereas the magnetoelectric coupling term χ_{em}^{yz} exhibits a real part with an antiresonant behavior. The magnitudes of the remaining returned surface susceptibility terms are all below 10^{-4} , thus they should be considered numerically zero. It is noted that the system of Eqs. (16) was solved with an error less than 10^{-3} at every frequency. The illustrated results, obtained by the proposed technique, are in very good agreement with the ones reported in the literature.^{18–21} Clearly, primary magnetic resonance at direction normal to the metasurface plane is illustrated, owing to the formation of magnetic moment in this direction, whereas electric resonance at the y -direction is also exhibited, accounting for the corresponding electric resonance. Magnetoelectric coupling at yz -direction reveals the expected bianisotropic behavior of the structure, due to the non-symmetry of the EC-SRR particles.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have successfully developed a novel fully numerical technique for the efficient retrieval of the effective surface susceptibilities of a composite periodic metasurface. Our powerful computational tool is utilized to obtain the required computational information of a unit cell, i.e., the dispersion diagrams and the microscopic field components of its supported modes: The dual field-flux FEM formulation scheme provides the essential computational capabilities to accurately return all field components and their derivatives at the same order of approximation, a crucial feature required for the implementation of our technique. Furthermore, a new field averaging

scheme is proposed for the acquisition of the average electromagnetic field components of the metasurface's surface modes, involving the integration of the field quantities above and below the structure under consideration. We subsequently utilize the generalized sheet transition conditions and by involving the aforementioned numerical information inside them, we derive a linear system of algebraic equations with the surface susceptibilities as unknowns. Numerical solution of this system of equations leads to the effective parameters of a general bianisotropic metasurface. The returned results for an EC-SRR metasurface are in very good agreement with the published ones in the literature. Accurate numerical data due to the utilized computational technique, along with the intrinsic eigenmode information of a simulated metastructure and the simultaneous avoidance of any wave excitation schemes or approximate analytical relations prove the robustness and correctness of the technique proposed in this work.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Michalis Nitas: Conceptualization (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – original draft (equal). **Maria Kafesaki:** Supervision (supporting). **Samel Arslanagic:** Supervision (lead).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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